

Andragogical Principles in the Professional Development of Academic Staff

Nataliia V. Dzhendzhero

Military Academy, Odesa, Ukraine

Abstract. The paper analyses the applicability of andragogical principles to the professional development of academic staff in a military higher-education institution. Theoretical frameworks of self-directed learning, problem-centred training and workplace learning are synthesised into a coherent andragogical platform for in-service development. The author argues that professional development of academic staff should be constructed around genuine pedagogical problems encountered in the classroom rather than around decontextualised content delivery, and that any sustainable programme must acknowledge the professional autonomy of adult learners. A modular in-service design is proposed, combining short thematic workshops, accompanied implementation cycles and structured peer observation across a twelve-month period. Particular attention is devoted to the conditions enabling self-directed learning among adult professionals — psychological safety, institutional recognition of effort and meaningful choice over developmental pathways. The paper concludes with managerial recommendations for orchestrating a sustainable in-service system and identifies directions for empirical evaluation.

Keywords: *andragogy; professional development; academic staff; self-directed learning; workplace learning; in-service design*

1. Background

The professional development of academic staff at military higher-education institutions is frequently organised as content-delivery events detached from the practical challenges of classroom teaching. Such arrangements underutilise the intellectual and motivational resources of the adult professional learner and produce limited transfer into teaching practice. Andragogical theory offers a systematic alternative predicated on the autonomy, experience and pragmatic orientation of adult learners.

2. Design Principles and Modular Structure

The proposed design rests on three synthetic principles. First, professional development must be problem-centred: its content is drawn from pedagogical difficulties and opportunities encountered in teaching practice, not from generic catalogues of topics. Second, it must be self-directed: participants exercise genuine choice over developmental pathways, with the institution providing structure, resources and recognition rather than prescription. Third, it must be embedded in the workplace: short, focused engagements with content alternate with accompanied implementation in the participant's own classroom and with structured peer observation. The twelve-month modular structure comprises six thematic workshops (four hours each), six accompanied implementation cycles (two to three weeks each), four peer-observation triads and one culminating professional-development review. The institutional scaffolding includes explicit protection of time, recognition of participation in career processes, and access to a shared repertoire of didactic resources.

3. Conclusions

A sustainable andragogical design for the professional development of academic staff requires coherent institutional support, attention to the psychological conditions of self-directed learning and a problem-centred orientation. Empirical evaluation should examine both proximal indicators, such as engagement and perceived transfer, and distal indicators, such as observable changes in teaching and cadet outcomes.

Note. *This extended abstract was prepared within the professional-development programme «Psychology and Pedagogy» (3.0 ECTS, 90 academic hours) delivered online by KUL in cooperation with EEUN; it accompanies Certificate of Professional Development No. 2026-03-UA-8, Lublin, 30 March 2026.*

Declaration on the use of AI. *Generative AI tools (large-language-model assistants) were used solely for language editing and stylistic refinement. The theoretical framework, conceptual argumentation, analysis and conclusions constitute the author's original work; the author assumes full responsibility for the integrity, accuracy and originality of the content. All AI-assisted editing complies with the COPE guidelines on the use of AI in scholarly publications and with the academic-integrity policy of KUL.*